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After Covid 19 Impact on Human Life

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ABSTRACT

2020 is one of the worst years in human history because of killing virus which is named as “corona virus” and COVID-19 this originated from Wuhan China and dispersal all over the world affecting millions of people worldwide. COVID-19 response has changed human life style in the entire world. The major change in impact on the environment can alter the direct interaction between people and nature far those concerned with animals as sources of novel people COVID-19 infection. Many Countries tried to make vaccines for COVID-19 and they kind of successful and some hope to people considering that many people recovered from this the thins will become normal once again in near human will over this life. The world’s response against COVID-19 shows the power of science and the willingness of scientists across the world to work together. Patients were isolated and identified within a few days of the pandemic, which paved the way for diagnostic kits, vaccines and treatments.

Keywords: environment, human life, nature, animals, vaccines

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INTRODUCTION

A novel corona virus named “2019” Novel ‘corona virus’ or ‘covid-19’ by the WHO (World Health Organization) ‘covid-19’ homologous for pneumonia and similar symptoms for pneumonia at the beginning of December 2019 in near Wuhan city (china) covid 19 is a pathogenic virus from the phylogenetic Analysis carried out with obtainable full genome sequences.

Bats occur to be the covid – 19 virus reservoirs but the intermediate host has not been detected till now. Though three major area of work already are ongoing in China to advise our of the pathogenic origin of the outbreak.

These include early inquiries of cases with symptoms occurring near in Wuhan during December 2019,

ecological sampling from the Human wholesale seafood market as well as other area markets. And collection of detailed report of the point of origin and type of wild life species market on the huanan market and the destination of those animals after the market has been closed.

The covid 19 response have dramatically changed people life styles in of the world. There major change in impact on the environment can alter the direct interaction between human and nature for beyond

those concerned with animals as sources of novel human corona virus infections.

The COVID 19 pandemic which has the most tragic consequences can also be global natural experiment in human nature. Infection that can provide mechanistic insights into the complex processes dynamics of their infection and into possible strategies then to best effect.

Areas in which COVID 19 has negatively impacted

Figure No. 1

Symptoms and Impacts

Corona virus attacks respiratory system. It is common symptom may in clued cough, cold, fever, lost of sense of taste and smell etc. Mainly affect old aged human and people with low immunity system. It spreads through air droplets by coughiy and sneening. This killing virus took may lives affected the manking very severey old aged people and the people who had low immunity died because of this virus. These virus millions of lives and considered as second most deadly pandemic of all time many people lost their jobs and economy was crashed.

Corrective Measures

To reduce the spread of this virus many countries imposed full lock down for many months. Masks and sanitizers become compulsory in life all the sports activities and social gathering were stopped and specially school and college were closed which affected many students.

Positive Outcomes

Due to this corona virus and pandemic there many outcomes like the environment become clean and the air become breathable people specially the lower close come to know about hygiene and cleanliness

Challenges

How many challenges in human life, public health issues employment and labour issues, in the COVID 19 arises food security human health issues and employment and labour issues in particular workers health and safety converge, workplace safety and health practices and ensuring access to decent work for protection of labour rights in all industries will be crucial in addressing the human dimensional crisis. Due to Corona virus, negative results were seen and heard. It is undeniable that this year many people lost their jobs and many families were seen struggling with physical and mental ailments. Due to the closure of schools, colleges and universities, the education of many children was affected and the students and teachers had to accept the changed education system in the emergency situation.

Impact of covid-19 on lifestyle-

- Health Conscious-Covid-19 taught us to value something the most, so that is health. During this time people added the importance of healthy eating, exercise, yoga etc. to their lifestyle and came to know to what extent we need to be alert to stay healthy. Then whether it is physical health or mental.
- Work from Home - The epidemic also assured people that professional work can also be done from work from home and good performance can be given. It was found that both the Employee and the Employer have benefited from this work culture.
- Online education-Children have been studying through online since two years and it has definitely had a mixed impact on the performance of teachers and students. Online virtual classes taught children the importance of self-study and learning in a new way, as well as teaching teachers with new challenges and how to build better relationships with students.

- Online Shopping - Adopted the method of online shopping and many small startup companies started working in this area. Many small shops, grocery shops, food and drink also started the system of home delivery, which increased many jobs in this field.
- The emphasis of yoga and ayurveda- Corona attracted people's attention towards Ayurveda, adopted to boost immunity and to keep physical and mental health better.
- Masks and social distance - The importance of maintaining the distance has been accepted.

CONCLUSION

Many countries tried to make vaccines for COVID 19 and they were kind of successful and gave some hope to people considering that many people recovers from this virus it seems that the thing will become normal once again in near future and human will over this life they developed may different types of vaccines like Infective vaccine, M-RNA fared vaccines (A new type of vaccines) and new develop in oral vaccines etc.

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